

Supplemental Materials S1

Expert Evaluation Questionnaire: Bridge Element Importance Assessment Using Fermatean Fuzzy AHP Questionnaire

Name:

Qualification:

Organization:

Years of Experience:

This questionnaire is designed to collect expert judgments on the importance of various bridge elements in assessing bridge condition and prioritizing maintenance activities. The study considers eighteen (18) bridge elements grouped into four main categories: deck, superstructure, substructure, and accessories.

You are kindly requested to provide pairwise comparisons of these bridge groups and their elements based on their relative importance with respect to the whole bridge structure. Please use the linguistic scale provided in Table I below for your comparisons. Your valuable input will be used to compute the relative weights of bridge components using the Fermatean Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy (FF-AHP) method, which will help in developing a framework for bridge condition evaluation and maintenance prioritization.

Table I: Linguistic variables and their score indices

Linguistic variables	Label	Score Index (SI)
Extremely high important	EHI	9
Very high important	VHI	7
High important	HI	5
Slightly high important	SHI	3
Equal important	EI	1
Slightly low important	SHI	1/3
Low important	LI	1/5
Very low important	VLI	1/7
Extremely low important	ELI	1/9

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Q4. Please rate the following pairs of substructure elements based on their structural importance in maintenance using the linguistic variables provided in Table I

No.	First element	vs	Second element	EHI	VHI	HI	SHI	EI	SHI	LI	VLI	ELI
1	Pier/Column	vs	Pier Cap/Cross Beam									
2	Pier/Column	vs	Abutment									
3	Pier/Column	vs	Pile									
4	Pier/Column	vs	Pile Cap									
5	Pier Cap/Cross Beam	vs	Abutment									
6	Pier Cap/Cross Beam	vs	Pile									
7	Pier Cap/Cross Beam	vs	Pile Cap									
8	Abutment	vs	Pile									
9	Abutment	vs	Pile Cap									
10	Pile	vs	Pile Cap									

Q5. Please rate the following pairs of accessories elements based on their importance in prioritizing bridge for maintenance using the linguistic variables provided in Table I

No.	First element	vs	Second element	EHI	VHI	HI	SHI	EI	SHI	LI	VLI	ELI
1	Curbs and Sidewalks	vs	Handrails and Pedestrian Railings									
2	Curbs and Sidewalks	vs	Barriers									
3	Curbs and Sidewalks	vs	Lighting and Electrical Systems									
4	Curbs and Sidewalks	vs	Drainage Systems									
5	Curbs and Sidewalks	vs	Signage and Markings									
6	Handrails and Pedestrian Railings	vs	Barriers									
7	Handrails and Pedestrian Railings	vs	Lighting and Electrical Systems									
8	Handrails and Pedestrian Railings	vs	Drainage Systems									
9	Handrails and Pedestrian Railings	vs	Signage and Markings									
10	Barriers	vs	Lighting and Electrical Systems									
11	Barriers	vs	Drainage Systems									
12	Barriers	vs	Signage and Markings									
13	Lighting and Electrical Systems	vs	Drainage Systems									
14	Lighting and Electrical Systems	vs	Signage and Markings									
15	Drainage Systems	vs	Signage and Markings									

Thank you for providing your valuable insights through this questionnaire